

Societal & Political Engagement
of Young People in Environmental Issues

D3.2: Integrated and Tested STEP Platform

WP3 – e-Participation platform integration

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Glossary of terms

Component terms	Description
Dialogue	Dialogue is a general term for a Citizen engagement activity/project.
Post	Inputs under dialogues, called as petition, observation and idea according to the dialogue type.
Item	Item is an abstract representation of social media messages published in different social media platforms. In other words an item can be a Tweet, a Facebook post, an image in Instagram, a video in YouTube, a comment on a video or a post etc.
Original Item	A field that indicates whether an item is an original item or a share of a previous one. This can be also used as filter.
Item Type	A field that indicates whether an item is a media item (i.e. contains an image or a video) or a text item. Can also be used as a filter.
Collection	A set of items representing a topic of interest defined by a user. Technically a collection is defined as a set of keywords and a set of social media accounts. The items associated with the collection are those that contain these keywords or are published by these accounts.
Topic	Topic is a subset of items in a collection associated with a specific subject/theme.
Feed	A view of items associated with a collection. These items can be refined by the application of filters as platform, language, publication date, etc.
Dashboard	A view of statistics related to a collection such as the total number of items and users in a collection, the most active users in a collection, the top mentioned entities and tags, locations with high activity etc.
Entities	Named entities e.g. persons, organizations, and tags identified in the text of the collected items. These entities highlight the semantics of items.
API	Application Programming Interface
DGT	Directorate-General for Translation
EMS	Experiment Management System
JRC	Joint Research Centre
LM	Language Model

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MT	Machine Translation
RBMT	Rule-based Machine Translation
REST	Representational State Transfer
SMT	Statistical Machine Translation
SRILM	SRI Language Modelling Toolkit
TTS	Text-to-Speech

1 *Executive summary*

The deliverable *D3.2 Integrated and Tested STEP Platform* is part of the **Work Package 3: e-Participation platform integration**. The purpose of this deliverable is to present the first version of the STEP platform, and to provide detailed information about the platform features according to its components and user types. The intended audience for this deliverable is preliminarily the project partners but the deliverable could be of interest also for the end users. The deliverable will support the work that will be carried out during Work Package 5: Pilot operation and evaluation.

The aim of this deliverable is to define the first version of the integrated and tested STEP Platform. The features of the platform have been described with the user interfaces according to user types and based on core components of the platform which are e-participation component, social media mining & visualisation component, machine translation & text to speech component and data logging component. Main features of each component have been described in detail. In addition, features provided for localization of the STEP Platform according to pilot requirements are also presented.

Testing procedures and testing results are discussed including description and execution of the tests performed. The results of the tests will guide project partners during the second period developments.

The present deliverable includes all aspects that have been taken into consideration during the development of the STEP platform and in addition covers risks/challenges based on each component as well as ethical, legal and data protection issues. In addition, the planning for the second period of the project is briefly presented.

2 Introduction

The aim of **D3.2 Integrated and Tested STEP Platform** deliverable is to present the first version of STEP platform. The deliverable includes the platform's features, presented mainly from the user and user interface point of view, as well as a description of the testing process, ethical issues and work done for the achievement of project objectives.

The general project requirements/objectives are fulfilled by STEP via a number of core components, which include:

- e-Participation component
- Machine Translation & Text to Speech component
- Social Media Mining & Visualization component
- Data Logging component

Chapter 3 provides detailed information about the STEP Platform including its main features according to components and user types.

Chapter 4 describes the testing procedure performed and its results.

Chapter 5 provides information about risks and challenges of each component that may be faced during the second period of the project.

Chapter 6 describes the next period planning including amendments and developments that will be performed during second period of the project.

Chapter 7 gives details about ethical, legal issues and data protection that were concerned during the implementation of the project.

2.1 General Concept of the STEP Platform

The STEP platform brings together several ideas and technologies with the goal to engage Young European Citizens and Public Authorities in decision making about environmental strategies, policies, plans, programmes, laws, and projects.

The main concepts underpinning the STEP project - also presented in Figure 1- are:

- **Integrated platform:** STEP will use social media / web mining technologies that will enable young people to view personalized and enriched information relevant to the topic they are viewing, filtered through multiple social media and web sources, in one unified environment. This eliminates the need to search for content on multiple platforms, and to navigate through the overflow of information available.
- **Engagement:** Social media analytics and monitoring tools will be used in order to facilitate the identification of the preferences of young people, and thus develop an effective strategy for engaging young citizens.
- **Motivation:** Social gamification techniques will be used for increasing motivation for participation of young citizens.
- **Removal of language barriers:** Machine translation technology will allow users to access content from other countries in their own language, removing language barriers and fostering cross-border interaction.

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- **Policy-making support:** Visual representations of results will enable policy makers to interpret the results of their campaigns, view patterns and spot trends, facilitating decision making.
- **Inclusion:** There will be specific actions for the inclusion of young people with fewer opportunities (because of social/economic obstacles, cultural differences, etc.), including dedicated workshops for those who are not familiar with the use of digital tools, info kiosks, and special dissemination material.

Figure 1 STEP underpinning ideas and impact

The STEP platform is based on a modular architecture, integrating individual components which are developed / adapted so that they can carry out specific business functions, and can be reused, each one individually, by public organizations for quickly opening their decision-making processes. This is especially important for public organizations that already have well set-up procedures for managing participation, and do not want to replace them. Public organizations can however benefit from the use of partial components of STEP, according to their needs, thus integrating them in their regular practice. For example, the social media / web mining component may be used by public organizations for identifying citizen trends, and the social media monitoring tool for planning effective participation strategies.

3 The STEP Platform

The STEP platform consists of four main components which are presented in Figure 2. The detailed information about the architecture of the platform and components are explained in the deliverable **D3.1 Architecture and Integration Framework Definition Specification**. This chapter presents the core features of the STEP platform which are e-participation, social media mining & visualization, machine translation & text to speech and data logging components.

Figure 2 STEP Platform architecture and components

Using the STEP platform Public Authorities will be able to:

- Create and publish dialogues on issues with an environmental impact, initiating talk table conversations to engage young citizens to express their ideas and participate in decision making-processes
- Collect, monitor and analyse results of the dialogues
- Identify impacts and spot trends
- Evaluate user choices such as level of usage of platform components, dialogue paths, use of system elements level of usage of user interface elements
- Motivate young citizens participation through gamification techniques (leaderboards and badges)
- Create reports and newsletters to inform about the results of dialogues

Using the STEP platform, Young citizens will be able to;

- Express their opinions about environmental issues and participate in decision making processes
- Be informed on what other people are saying on the specific issues of interest, filter relevant information from noisy content on social media and web streams
- Monitor their contributions, get feedback on the results of the processes in which they have participated, and on how their contribution has made a difference
- View personalised and enriched information on emerging topics from social media and the web, relevant to the consultation they are participating in

3.1 E-Participation Component

The cloud e-Participation component is the central module of the STEP platform, allowing the interaction between end users (policy makers and young people) and the communication with the other platform components. In this section the e-participation component is described in detail according to the following;

- Features of front page
- Features for public authority users
- Features for young citizens
- Localization of the platform
- Native mobile applications of the platform

Considering the aim of the STEP platform there are two classes of users which are Public Authority users and Young Citizens, and four different user types as follows;

- Public Authority Admin
- Public Authority User (Analyst)
- Young Citizen (Creator)
- Non-registered User (Rookie)

Each user type has different rights and access to different features accordingly.

3.1.1 Features of the front page

The first version of the STEP e-participation platform consisting of main components and features has been delivered and is accessible from <https://step.green/>.

Figure 3 Front page of step.green

Different engagement activities have been placed on the front page of the platform in order to allure visitors click on the website. The activities that can be reached from the front page are:

- 'Share ideas for a greener Europe' dialogue
- Timeline feature
- Meet other greensters

3.1.1.1 *General Dialogue for all European Citizens: 'Ideas for a greener Europe'*

On the front page, a general dialogue for all European citizens has been created in order to collect ideas all around Europe on how Europe can be better and greener. Similar ideas will be clustered to innovative concepts/bigger ideas that can be shared to European policy makers and by the general public.

Figure 4 'Ideas for a greener Europe' dialogue page

3.1.1.2 Timeline feature

The general timeline on the front page is a poll which seeks to engage young citizens to place events on a timeline and thereby leave their footprint on how Environment in Europe should be prioritized. After submitting their own input, young citizens will be able to see the average (collective) result and also how the other participants' inputs are spread over time/impact among different users.

Figure 5 Timeline page

3.1.1.3 Co-creation feature: 'Meet other greensters'

Young citizens will be able to co-create insights and ideas for their own future steps with the help of a social media mining tool integrated into the STEP platform. If they wish they can meet and discuss with a group of people from all over Europe.

Figure 6 'Meet other greensters' page

3.1.2 Features for Public Authority Users

A Public Authority (PA) user can be either admin or analyst. PA admin is the administrator of the local platform and has all rights. PA Analysts have instead limited rights compared to the admins. Analysts don't have rights for the following;

- Create dialogues
- Create conversations and round table dialogues
- Full access to social media monitoring tool and admin panel.

3.1.2.1 General management

PA admin has access to the admin panel where she/ he can manage various aspects of the platform. In particular, dialogues, participants, admin profile, municipality profile, email templates, etc. are managed through the admin panel.

Figure 7 Admin panel page

3.1.2.2 Dialogue management

Dialogue is a general term for a Citizen engagement activity/project. PA admins are able to set up dialogues about issues that have environmental impacts. There are three dialogue types: e-petition, observation and idea dialogues.

- **E-petition dialogue** is created to obtain young citizen’s suggestions and petitions.
- **Observation dialogue** is created to allow young citizens to share what they observe in their surrounding environment.
- **Idea dialogue** is created in order to gather ideas from young citizens.

Figure 8 Dialogue types in the platform

Figure 9 An example of e-petition dialogue page

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PA admin can invite participants to the dialogues using their emails and she/he assigns roles to users. There are four types of roles for dialogues which are citizen, PA analyst, PA admin and dialogue admin. Analysts can also invite participants if admin gives them the required rights.

Figure 10 Inviting participants to the dialogues

There are different options available for dialogues. PA admin is able to create **public dialogues** which will be open to everyone, and **private dialogues** which will be open to invited participants only. Since unregistered users have some rights, PA admin can choose if **registration** is required or not. Users need to provide full name, postal address, age and gender prior to submit or sign their posts. With an **SMS verification** option extended validation of users can be provided. Furthermore, PA admin is able to **monitor incoming posts**. If this option is selected, user's posts will not be published without confirmation.

Figure 11 SMS verification

Figure 12 Monitoring posts

3.1.2.3 Posts management

PA admin is able to create posts under dialogues. These posts are called differently according to dialogue types. Posts are called as petitions in e-petition dialogue, as observations in observation dialogue and as ideas in idea dialogue. Images, videos, sound files, locations or Youtube links can be added to posts.

Figure 13 Post types

Figure 14 Creating posts

PA admin handles incoming posts by tagging and sorting, editing, copying and moving to other dialogues. In addition, posts can be shared with social media (Facebook, Twitter, LinkedIn, Google+) to inform citizens and get support. PA users can support petitions by signing them. Feedback is given by leaving comments to posts; also PA users can send private comments to post owners to give private feedback. Both admin and analyst can evaluate posts by ranking them on a scale from 0 to 10.

Figure 15 Handling incoming posts

Figure 16 Signing, commenting and rating petitions

Posts can be viewed in different view modes which are portrait, landscape, wide and map views. In addition, it is possible to create posts in a map view by selecting a specific location on the map.

Figure 17 Different view modes

Figure 18 Map view of posts and creation of posts in map view

3.1.2.4 Analysis of dialogues

PA users are able to analyse dialogues. Analysis of the dialogues shows how many posts have been made, how many of them are rated and commented on by admins and analysts. Graphical views of posts that have been made over time are presented in the platform in the analysis section.

Figure 19 Analysis of dialogues

3.1.2.5 Conversation and round table management

PA admin is able to create interactive conversations with selected dialogue participants. In addition, she/he can create virtual round table dialogues to discuss a specific issue with 5-10 selected participants.

Figure 20 Conversations and virtual round table dialogues

3.1.2.6 Report and newsletter management

Reports can be created and published within the platform to inform users about the results of the dialogues. In addition, these reports can be extracted as PDF and PAs can use them for the decision making procedures. Another document that can be created in the platform is the newsletter. PA admin can create and publish newsletters to present information and news about dialogues. In addition, subscription lists can be created for newsletters.

Figure 21 Creating reports

Figure 22 Creating newsletters

3.1.2.7 Gamification

Young citizens will be motivated through gamification techniques via leaderboards, badges and rating of posts. Young people will be encouraged to participate and develop their profile. Users gain points by participating in dialogues, creating, signing and commenting on posts. Then, the leaderboard is built according to the points gained and badges are awarded. Therefore, it is possible to see individual contributions and to provide motivation for active participation of young citizens.

LEADERBOARD	
	Naci Şen Citizen
Dialogue score:	24
Profile Score:	28
	Deneme Rookie
Dialogue score:	14
Profile Score:	107
	Leyla Yanmaz Dialogue admin
Dialogue score:	2
Profile Score:	175
	Panagiota Syropoulou Citizen
Dialogue score:	2
Profile Score:	56
	Άρης Γκούσκος Citizen
Dialogue score:	2
Profile Score:	10

Figure 23 Leaderboard

3.1.2.8 Social media mining & visualisation

PA admin is able to reach enriched information about emerging topics which are currently trending in social media and the web by capturing automated spottings. In addition, she/he is able to gain valuable insights from citizen contributed contents from social media/web via the social media monitoring tool. The visualisation tool provides an analysis of the collections created. The social media mining and visualisation feature is explained in detail in the Chapter 3.2.

3.1.3 Features for Young Citizens

Young citizens are called ‘creator’ if they are registered to the platform and ‘rookie’ if not registered to the platform. Users can register to the STEP platform by providing name, e-mail address, gender and year of birth; however unregistered users are welcome with limited rights. Users may also use their social media accounts (Facebook, Twitter, LinkedIn, Google+) to login.

Figure 24 Registration page

Figure 25 Login page

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Young citizens will use the STEP platform to express their ideas and opinions, to show their observations, and hence to be actively engaged in decision-making processes of PAs. Young citizens are able to view and join public dialogues. They can also join private dialogues via invitations received from PA admins.

Figure 26 Joining dialogues

Once young citizens have joined in a dialogue, they are able to create posts under this dialogue. According to the dialogue settings, they may be able to create posts without joining the dialogue and even without registering to the platform.

They can share posts through social media (Facebook, Twitter, LinkedIn, Google+) to get support for their posts.

Figure 27 Sharing posts with social media

Young citizens are able to see other posts under dialogues and this will help them see other people's thoughts and suggestions. They can discuss petitions, ideas and observations by leaving comments. Young citizens can sign other users' petitions to support them, which means that she/he agrees with the proposed petition.

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Figure 28 Viewing dialogue posts

Posts can be viewed in different view modes; portrait, landscape, wide and map. Young citizens are able to create posts in map view by selecting a specific location on the map.

Young citizens are able to join conversations that have been created under dialogues by PA admins. Therefore, it is possible to engage users in real-time conversations (chats) with administrators, other local PA representatives (analysts) and other local citizens. Young citizens can also join round table discussions created about a specific topic by PA admins.

Figure 29 Joining conversations

Figure 30 Joining round table discussions

Since language barriers are removed in the STEP platform via the machine translation component, users are able to reach and understand dialogues in other languages. Text to speech feature is available for English, Turkish, Spanish, Italian, Greek, Catalan, and Swedish. These features are explained in detail in Section 3.3.

Young citizens are able to reach enriched information about emerging topics which are currently trending in social media and the web according to their interests via the integrated social media mining tool. Detailed information about this feature is given in Section 3.2.

3.1.4 Localization of the STEP Platform

Localization of the STEP platform is implemented in two different aspects;

- Translation of local resources of the platform and availability of STEP in each pilot's own language
- Localization of pilot requirements based on the flows and processes of the STEP platform components.

The STEP platform has been translated into the language of the pilot partners using a translation tool.

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Key	English Step	Swedish Step	Greek Step	Turkish Step	Catalonian Step	Spanish Step	Italian Step
(C) are typing...	(C) are typing...	(C) skriver...	(C) minipoloyou...	(C) yazıyor...	(C) estan escrivint...	(C) esta escribiendo...	stanno scrivendo
(C) is typing...	(C) is typing...	(C) skriver...	(C) minipoloyou...	(C) yazıyor...	(C) esta escrivint...	(C) esta escribiendo...	sta scrivendo
account.profile female							
account.profile male							
account.profile user							
challenge.details.normalize							
challenge.details.normalize							
in							
Department: unit, group of customers, segments. What behaviors, needs and requirements does this...and what the	Department: unit, group of customers, segments. What behaviors, needs and requirements does this...and what the	Varför kommer denna deltagare bli en succé? Beskriv vad som är mest utmärkt och sammanfattningsvis förklara varför du tror på detta.	Πώς να γίνει αυτό; Οδηγίες, πληροφορίες, συμβουλές, προτάσεις, κ.λπ.	Böşüm için diğer kullanıcıları segmentler hakkında bilgileri paylaşarak görüşlerinizi bildirebilirsiniz.	Departament: unitat, grup de clients, segments. «Quins comportaments, necessitats i requeriments té aquest... i el que	Departamento: unidad, grupo de clientes, segmentos. «¿Qué comportamientos, necesidades y requerimientos tiene esto... y lo que	Department: unita, gruppo di clienti, segmenti. Quali comportamenti, esigenze e necessità ha questo
concept become a success? Describe what is brilliant and summarize why the target audience will love the	concept become a success? Describe what is brilliant and summarize why the target audience will love the	Varför kommer denna deltagare bli en succé? Beskriv vad som är mest utmärkt och sammanfattningsvis förklara varför du tror på detta.	Πώς να γίνει αυτό; Οδηγίες, πληροφορίες, συμβουλές, προτάσεις, κ.λπ.	Konseptin başari olmasini mi açıklarım? Fikrinizi paylaşarak diğer kullanıcıların görüşlerini bildirebilirsiniz.	concept sera un exit? Describe ciò que és brillant i resume per què el públic objectiu li encantarà	concepto sera un éxito? Describe lo que es brillante y resume porque al público objetivo le encantará	concepto sarà un successo? Descrivi questo che è brillante e riassumi perché il pubblico obiettivo ama

Figure 31 Translation tool

Pilot's accounts have been created within the platform and are accessible from the following links in their local language;

- Association of the Communities of Locride (<https://it.step.green/locride>)
- Mollet des Valles Municipality (<https://cat.step.green/molletvalles>)
- Valdemoro Municipality (<https://es.step.green/valdemoro>)
- Region of Crete (<https://gr.step.green/crete>)
- Hatay Metropolitan Municipality (<https://tr.step.green/hatay>)

Figure 32 Front pages of STEP pilots

The following features have been deployed to the STEP platform after considering specific requests from the pilots:

- Gender and age data have been added to the registration process (optional to add on municipality level)
- Various embeddable Snippets for pilot homepages of their websites have been provided through the STEP Platform
- Non-registered user type has been included to sign and comment on existing petitions without registering (with name, gender, age, postal code and optional e-mail)
- Dialogues can be seen in map view and petitions are created by selecting location on the map

3.1.5 Mobile application of the STEP platform

Native mobile applications of the STEP platform are also under development for iOS and Android. The mobile applications will be delivered in the second period of the project.

Figure 33 Sample STEP mobile interfaces

Some features of the mobile application are as follows;

- Reaching front page after login, choosing city/municipality
- Landing page per city/municipality
- Viewing dialogues and posts
- Creating posts under dialogues with image, video, sound file, location or YouTube film
- Chatting with dialogue owner or other participants.

3.2 Social Media Mining and Visualization Component

This component is based on a pre-existing tool for social media mining described in deliverable D3.1: “Architecture and Integration Framework Definition Specification” and the effort in Period 1 pertained to its adaptation and setup to function in accordance with the user requirements described in deliverable D2.2: “Report on Users’ Needs and Technical Requirements”. As the only prerequisite for the social media monitoring tool is a machine with a running instance of Docker¹ and Docker Compose, the effort for the STEP

¹ [https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Docker_\(software\)](https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Docker_(software))

project was spent mainly in the deployment of the tool on top of Docker². The back-end functionality of the tool remained the same as the pre-existing version and it sufficiently covers the core of the requirements for the first version of the platform. The UI was adapted accordingly to meet the requirements of the rest platform.

Two main views of the tool have been integrated in the STEP platform:

- Full view: This is the full version of the tool allowing the authorities to plan their environmental campaigns, monitor interesting environmental issues, and analyse results using the component's dashboard, feed and visualisations. Only PA admin has access to full view of the tool.
- Reduced view: This is a reduced version of the tool which is integrated in the STEP platform allowing citizens to declare their topics of interest and receive relevant content items from social media. These can be consequently used as regular content items in the context of the e-participation component. Other users except PA admin have access to reduced view of the tool.

This component is a web application that enables users to discover how content is shared in Online Social Networks. It covers the most popular social media sharing platforms, namely Facebook, Twitter, Google+, YouTube, and Flickr. In addition, to Social Networks, the application also supports RSS Feeds. The component continuously collects information around PA user or young citizens provided target entities. Furthermore it monitors the content posted by manually defined and related social media accounts.

3.2.1 Full view of the tool

PA admin has access to the full view of the social media mining tool. She/he can reach to full version of the tool from the STEP Platform.

Figure 34 Reaching social media mining tool

The component consists of three parts which are input, feed and dashboard.

² For more details on the architecture of social media monitoring tool check: <https://github.com/MKLab-ITI/mmdemo-dockerized>

- **Input:** This part allows PA admin to create several collections; each one linked to a point of interest of his/her preferences. To initiate a collection user must define a set of keywords/hashtags and a set of user profiles, across Social Networks, all relevant to a topic he/she wants to inform about. Once user has launched a collection he/she can inspect all the gathered information in two primary sections: the Feed and the Dashboard.

Figure 35 Input in social media mining tool

- **Feed:** The Feed presents the latest media items collected around the topic in real time. The component fetches all relevant media content, photos, videos and posts, seconds to minutes after they are published. Each item contains all the information that comes along with the post such as time, user and Social Network. A number of filters and sorting criteria are available so that the feed can be customized to the needs of the end user. In more detail filters are as follows:
 - Social Network: Define the source of posts
 - Language: Define the language of posts
 - Topics: Define the topic provided from topic detection algorithm
 - Original: Define either the post is shared or original
 - Type: Define if post contains multimedia content or just text
 - Date: Define a specific time window

In addition, it is possible for users to sort contents according to following;

- Recent: The most recent posts come up
- Popularity: The most shared posts come up
- Relevance: The most relevant posts comes up

The user can also search for media based on specific keyword inside the collection.

Figure 36 Feed page in the social media mining tool

- **Dashboard:** This section offers a variety of metrics and widgets that offer summary views over the collected data, enabling users to gain meaningful insights about the entity (e.g. persons, organizations, and tags identified in the text of the collected items) of interest. The visualizations are interactive and allow users to inspect the media that are behind these statistics.

Figure 37 Dashboard page in social media mining tool (1/2)

Figure 38 Dashboard page in social media mining tool (2/2)

3.2.2 Reduced view of the tool

Since this is a reduced view of the component integrated into the STEP platform, all users are able to reach the tool from their personal pages. Users are able to capture automated trendspottings according to their interests defined by pre-set keywords.

Figure 39 Social media mining tool for citizens

Figure 40 Capturing automated trendspotting

3.3 Machine Translation and Text to Speech

The Machine Translation (MT) systems for the language pairs English - Spanish, English - Italian and English - Greek was built in Period 1. The two main approaches used to develop the MT systems are:

- Knowledge-driven: based on exploiting the expert experience of lexicographers and linguists, who write lexicons and grammar rules manually, founded on their own knowledge (RBMT = rule-based machine translation).
- Data-driven: based on automatic corpus analysis and statistical learning methods, where both translations and the rules are learned from a sufficient amount of bilingual corpora, i.e. from existing translations (SMT = Statistical MT).

In the STEP project, the SMT approach with a phrase-based translation model and the associated machine learning techniques is adopted. The phrase-based model is the most widely used approach. Instead of learning the translations word by word, larger word sequences (currently, up to 7 words) are being taken into account. Thus, larger contexts, different word orders in source and target, as well as distant dependencies were considered. However, very long dependences remain unseen and cannot be learned.

The development has been performed for those language pairs where sufficient parallels text corpora were available, i.e. for:

Figure 41 MT component language pairs

The Text-to-Speech component has been implemented with broad functionalities to allow flexible access from the STEP platform. Supported languages are Catalan, English (British and American), Greek, Italian, Spanish, Turkish, and Swedish. It can convert any text into an audio file. Both WAV and MP3 format are supported. The following voice parameters can be specified:

- Speed
- Pitch
- Volume
- Male or female voice for each language

3.3.1 Main features of the component

Users are able to see platform inputs (dialogues and posts) in their local languages due to the translation tools. The MT tool allows users to access content from other countries in their own language. There are translation icons in the dialogues and petitions that will open the translation machine. Translation of dialogues and posts English to/from Spanish, and Italian is presently available. Greek, Turkish and Catalan will be implemented during the second period of the project.

Text to speech feature for dialogues and posts allows the use of the STEP platform by visually impaired persons. It is also available for English, Turkish, Spanish, Italian, Greek, Catalan, and Swedish. There are text to speech icons on the dialogues and posts that read the text.

Figure 42 Machine translation & text to speech

The development of the MT systems comprised the following components:

- Training component for translation models (bilingual phrase tables) and for reordering models (bilingual “rules” how to deal with different word orders in source and target language).
- Tuning component for better adjusting the translation parameters according to the given domain or text genre; it is based on an extra set of human translations that is representative for the intended translation task in terms of vocabulary and style.
- Decoding component with powerful search algorithms that computes all possible translation hypotheses and finds the translation with the highest probability.
- Support for externally estimated LMs and integration of LM tools (SRILM, IRSTLM etc.), as well as already integrated LM software (KenLM, RandLM).
- Work-flow control tool (EMS = experiment management system), which enables the user to automate the whole training-tuning-evaluation chain; it offers a graphical interface to follow the progress of each step visually.

While the software components are basically language-independent, the language-specific system development required the collection and compilation of many different bilingual and monolingual resources:

- Bilingual: parallel training corpora, parallel reference translations for tuning and testing purposes, bilingual lexicons.
- Monolingual: large amounts of data in the target language for language modelling, linguistic resources and lexica for normalisation and pre-processing tasks.

The MT systems have been trained on freely available open source corpora, such as Europarl, DGT, JRC, and on parallel corpora crawled by Linguatrec.

3.3.1.1 *Crawler and HTML Parser:*

A bilingual crawler was developed which uses seed URLs. When crawling web sites, it first looks for pages with an identifiable language flag. For each found page, a corresponding parallel page is searched (in another language). In case such page is found, the crawler performs some checks: Does the translation contain a minimum of text? Do the pages indeed contain different and required languages? Are the texts most probably translations of each other (similar length, same numbers, same named entities, etc.)? The crawled documents are stored in HTML-format, and then processed offline by the HTML-parser.

3.3.1.2 *Sentence splitter and Tokenizer:*

The crawled texts were divided into sentences, which are the standard unit in language processing, and the basis of all following analysis tasks. In order to really be able to find parallel sentences, it is very important to harmonise the segmentation in both languages and to use similar heuristics for the detection of sentence boundaries (e.g. semicolon as sentence end in both languages). The Tokeniser detaches punctuation marks, symbols, brackets etc. from words.

3.3.1.3 *Sentence aligner:*

Alignment aims at identifying corresponding sentences in two given parallel texts. There are several open-source or commercial alignment tools in existence. Some of them take original texts as input and have integrated sentence segmentation and tokenisation tasks. However, our experiments have shown better

results if the input to the alignment task is already pre-processed and segmented on the paragraph level. Best results are achieved with Hunalign³, an open-source language-independent alignment tool, which also can make use of bilingual dictionaries if any are provided. In absence of bilingual dictionaries, Hunalign builds an automatic dictionary during a first alignment pass, and realigns the sentences in a second pass, using this dictionary.

3.3.1.4 Language modelling:

The goal of language modelling for MT is to assign a probability to a sequence of words, i.e. to a translation hypothesis. The language model allocates higher probability to frequent observed sequences of words and penalizes the rarely occurring ones. There are several tools for language modelling, such as SRILM (Stolcke, 2002), IRSTLM (Federico et al., 2008), KenLM (Heafield, 2010)) etc. For the language model estimation SRILM is used.

The advantage of n-gram LMs is that such models are corpus-based and as such reflect the “real world”. They are in particular suitable for languages with a stronger word order, since they perfectly reproduce local syntax and also semantics (usually, LMs with up to 3 or 4-grams are used in MT). The disadvantage of 3/4-gram LMs is that long distance dependencies cannot be reflected and the languages with flexible word order are more difficult to be mapped into a model. However, there is no much sense in using longer order, since it would make the language models very huge and slow, while the probability for longer and longer sequences (6, 7 or more) to be seen again is getting lower and lower.

3.4 Data Logging Component

The logging component is developed to be used for the evaluation of user-system interactions by logging both user actions and system events. It is designed as a REST web service and its communication is handled with JSON format. Logged data can be broken down by relevant categories like age, gender, etc. and will be used for the evaluation of user-system interactions.

STEP uses anonymous aggregation of user choices and interface accessing. This gives an accurate log of how users actually use the system. This data log informs about the following;

- The level of usage of the different parts of the software.
- Use (timing, type, level) of system elements.
- Level of usage of User Interface elements (which buttons, sliders, etc. are pressed, when and how often).

In addition, a reporting interface is developed for users to enable them to reach log information.

3.4.1 Main features of the component

The Data Logging system keeps the data about user-system interactions and system events. This component tracks each process of the user and covers the following: user profile management, visited pages, visited profiles, visited topics, comment and content operations and joining chat rooms. All interaction events in the STEP Platform are logged in the system. The Logging component also provides interfaces for all other modules to log their system events through several processes. Main Features of data logging component are as follows:

³ See: <http://mokk.bme.hu/resources/hunalign/>

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- Logging user activities such as membership, visits, and challenges.
- Storing these data in a way that can be interpreted as meaningful information and can be reported in various ways.

Logging efforts have value and are important for several reasons. In addition to supporting audits of selected system activity, security measures, and controls, a logging program can also help to resolve operational problems and contribute valuable information to security incident investigations. The Data Logging Component provides tracking user-system interactions. The system can report and show graphics to user for the following via log table data:

- Last logged
- Last changed password time
- Tracking logged IPs.
- Visited challenges
- Searched texts

The data logging system keeps data about user-system interactions. The system tracks each user process. The data logging covers the following topics: user profile operations, visited pages, visited profiles, visited topics, comment and content operations and joining chat rooms.

4 Testing of the STEP Platform

Unit testing, integration testing, user interface testing and security testing have been performed to ensure that the STEP platform meets its requirements and expected features properly. During the testing process the approaches described in the deliverable D3.1: “Architecture and Integration Framework Definition Specification” were followed. Load testing (stress tests) and user acceptance testing will be performed during the second period of the project.

4.1 Description of the test process

Test scenarios were prepared for various user types (rookie, analyst, admin) and executed. The aim was to write scenarios that would be easily read, understood and executed by someone who has not been previously involved with the project. The scenarios are described in the form of steps that someone has to follow in order to bring the system to the desired state.

Once the scenarios were written by test analysts, they were reviewed by other team members and the scenarios were then updated. Given the fact that the scenarios were written before the platform was ready, they’ve been checked multiple times through the process of asking clarification and they were adapted during test execution.

The next step was to decide which of them could be automated. The decision was based on the importance of the feature in combination with the difficulty of automating it. For example it was considered that the log in functionality was of high importance and it was one of the first tests included in the automated test suite. On the contrary, the chat functionality is a complicated one to automate and it was decided to only test it manually.

Tests were written independently of each other, and given that the tests run against the production environment, that would not cause any problem to the platform.

For the automation of the scenarios Selenium Webdriver⁴ was used and the tests were written in Java. 21 test steps were automated and run this way.

4.2 Test execution process

Once the system was ready, test execution was performed and all automated tests were completed. The features that were automated were also manually tested as there is always a need for a human eye to look at the system. In total 265 scenario steps were prepared to be tested. 237 of the scenario steps passed the test, while 19 of them failed and 9 of them are pending. Developments and amendment are being carrying out for the failed and pending steps.

⁴ See: http://www.seleniumhq.org/docs/03_webdriver.jsp

5 Risks and Challenges

What follows is a description of risks and challenges for each component of STEP:

- **E-participation component:** There could be issues related to the integration of the platform components due to amendments that will be performed in the second period of the project. In addition, during the pilot operation and evaluation process, pilots may ask for features that could change the architecture of the platform.
- **Social media mining & visualization:** One of the greatest challenges pertains to the separation between useful/relevant content and noise/spam. To this end, sophisticated topic detection, content selection and ranking mechanisms are necessary (increased effort will be put to their development in the coming period). Another challenge that the component faces pertains to the management of very large amounts of content and especially the real-time extraction of analytics by submitting aggregation-intensive queries to the database. To address this challenge, appropriate content deletion, offline aggregation and caching mechanisms need to be put in place. A risk for the component stems from its reliance on third-party APIs for data collection. For instance, as of June 2016, it is no longer possible to monitor content from Instagram (unless a special application is approved by Instagram). Changes in the ToS of the major social media APIs are continuously monitored and appropriate actions are taken when deemed necessary.
- **Machine translation and text to speech:** For machine translation, availability of sufficient training corpora could be a challenge. The development of Statistical Machine Translation (SMT) requires access to large bilingual corpora for training and optimizing the systems. For each language pair the availability of such corpora is different. As for Catalan and Turkish language, there are no corpora available from EU sources such as European Parliament, DGT or JRC. Currently alternative sources are being investigated. For text to speech, achieving correct pronunciation is an important issue. Although the linguistic data base covers large vocabularies, it may miss some terms (e.g. neologisms). If necessary, the linguistic database needs to be expanded. Another challenge is maintaining stability and performance of the component. As MT and TTS requires significant CPU and memory resources, the workload and performance resulting from the STEP platform and its users need to be carefully monitored. If necessary, architectural changes or additional hardware will be evaluated.
- **Data logging:** For new applications and their related operations, choosing constraints and maintaining an order can be a problem. Extending the logging system can cause some unexpected compatibility issues for the reporting system.

6 Next Period Planning

What follows is a description of the next period planning for each component:

- **E-participation component:**
 - Adaptation of the STEP platform according to pilot requirements will be performed.
 - All integrations will be completed.
 - Features for creating reports and newsletters will be improved.
 - Mobile application of the STEP platform for IOS and Android will be released.
- **Social media mining & visualization:**
 - a) Advanced content analytics, including:
 - Content item rating. Users will be able to rate the significance of specific content items in the feed; they will also be able to discard them from a collection if they find them irrelevant.
 - Filter out content items containing specific keywords
 - Extended monitoring of selected items. The user will be able to select specific content items (e.g. campaign announcements) for which further content collection will be performed, such as retweets, responses, post comments and endorsements.
 - b) New algorithmic and analysis approaches. Specifically:
 - Sorting content items based on ratings and similarity. A new algorithm will be implemented that will allow re-sorting of the feed content every time a user rates a content item, based on the similarity of the rated content to other content items.
 - Social media accounts recommendations. With a new algorithm, social media accounts (twitter accounts, Facebook pages etc.) will be automatically suggested to the user at query formation time, whenever the user enters a new topic of interest.
 - Improved topic detection and topic-based retrieval. Advanced algorithms will be used to achieve higher relevance of the topic categories discovered by the topic detection feature.
 - c) Improved query formation. New features include:
 - Geo-located search. Users will be able to create collections according to a specific geographic area of their interest.
 - Keyword filtering at query time, Users will be able to exclude specific keywords from their search when placing their topics of interest, i.e. they will be able to declare topics that are irrelevant to their search.
 - d) Pilot site-based user and content management. Collections will be restricted for viewing only among members of the same pilot site.
 - e) More animations and visualisations
 - In the dashboard: New animations of the emerging entities will be developed visualizing the temporal evolution of the entities frequency.
 - In the citizens view: New visualisations from the authorities' dashboard will be integrated in the citizens view.

- f) Feeding e-participation conversations through automated discovery of relevant social media content
 - The e-participation component will allow the automatic discovery of content from social media, relevant to specific posts made by a user. In this context a user will not be required to place his/her topics of interest, instead an intelligent algorithm will figure them out, mining the user's posts.
 - **Machine translation and text to speech:**
 - Machine translation for English from/to Greek, Turkish and Catalan will be released.
 - **Data logging**
 - User operations reporting interface will be improved.

7 Ethical, Legal Issues and Data Protection

Guidelines presented in deliverable D2.3: “Guidelines for handling ethical, legal issues and data protection” are followed by all partners during the STEP platform development and actions taken are listed in the following;

- All co-design workshop participants are informed by a written information sheet about the research, protocol, risks they could face and research benefits. In addition, participant informed consent was obtained from each participant. The information sheet and participant consent examples are presented in Appendix A.1 and Appendix A.2.
- Parental consent forms that include information about the project and permission for their child to participate co-design sessions are obtained while Involving minors (age 16-18) in the research groups. Related form is presented in Appendix A.3.
- Powerful authentication & authorization mechanism is provided to ensure authorized access to the platform’s data, the generation, maintenance and transmission of strong passwords.
- User Access Control Mechanism that provides the right privileges to the platform users is provided.
- Additional security mechanisms including SQL injection, cross-site scripting (XSS) and session hijacking are provided.
- The platform supports secure protocols (SSL) and encryption mechanisms to allow the secure transmission of sensitive information over the network.
- The platform is hosted on a secure data center infrastructure, which is controlled by the coordinator, DRAXIS.
- The project performs and will perform user studies and tests during its research and evaluation stages. For the conduction of the user studies no personal sensitive data is required and informed consents will be collected.
- Following the best practice for ethics in Human-Computer Interaction, any personal (but not sensitive) data collected during the user evaluations is anonymized or at least pseudonymized and used for the purposes of the project.
- The participation is voluntary and informed consent is collected from each individual user.
- Information Sheet is provided to each contacted individual, informing them about the scope of the research and where additional information can be sought.

8 Conclusion

D3.2 Integrated and Tested STEP Platform deliverable presented detailed information for the platform that have been delivered in the first period of the project. The main goal of the deliverable is to define the first version of the integrated and tested STEP platform and to describe main features of the platform and each component, which are e-participation component, social media mining & visualisation component, machine translation & text to speech component and data logging component.

Since the platform features has been presented in detail from end user perspective by providing related user interfaces, the deliverable has provided an overview about the usage of the platform for end users. Features of the STEP platform have been described according to the following aspects;

- Features of the front page
- Features for Public Authority users
- Features for Young Citizens
- Localization of the STEP platform
- Mobile application of the STEP platform

Testing of the STEP platform has been explained including test description and test execution processes. Testing of the first version of the platform provided feedback for the parts that need changes and developments. The results of the testing process will guide technical partners during the second period of the project.

In the document, chapters for risks and challenges that may be faced for each component and next period planned actions have been included. In addition, ethical, legal and data protection issues considered during the project execution have been covered.

The outcome of the deliverable will be a reference for pilot partners. Pilot partners will start to use the platform for defined scenarios and each aspect of the platform will be tested during the Work Package 5 'Pilot operation and Evaluation'. After monitoring the pilot execution and receiving pilot's feedbacks, required developments and changes will be implemented for the final version of the platform.

Appendix A.1

CO-DESIGN INFORMATION SHEET

GOAL

The project *SocieTal and political Engagement of young People in environmental issues* (STEP) seeks to engage young people in discussions about environmental policies, in particular offering an opportunity to discuss their ideas with policymakers, with an online platform, via social media and mobile applications. The project is funded by the European Commission Under the call YOUNG-5b-2014: "Societal and political engagement of young people and their perspectives on Europe".

During the coming two months, as part of the project we will conduct some co-design sessions with both policy makers and young people across Europe. These sessions will help us define and shape the form of the online platform we are creating. You therefore have the opportunity to be part of this interesting project and your input will be considered for the design.

BENEFITS

At this stage, our goal is to involve the users early in the design process and empower them to contribute actively to the final shape of the STEP platform. The users/participants who will participate, will have a relevant role in shaping how the STEP platform will be developed. Indeed our research goal is to listen and make sure that the user's needs are taken in account in the development process.

PARTICIPATION

Your participation will always be voluntary and as participant you can withdraw at any time from the research. On this occasion, we aim at conducting a design session lasting between 1.5 – 2 hours.

The session will be conducted in the school environment and will be done in English (with support from a native Spanish/Catalan speaker). The session will be conducted by a professional researcher from Abertay (<http://www.abertay.ac.uk>) a University based in Scotland.

The session should not carry any major discomfort. All the tasks will be paper based and focused on your engagement with environmental issues and social media. Should any task provide discomfort you always have the right to refuse to participate. You will be required to sign a consent form to take part and if you are under 18 we also require parental consent (forms will be given to you to sign).

CONFIDENTIALITY/ANONYMITY

The data collected will contain minimal personal information about you except your age and current occupation.

Your designs and material produced in the session will be used for the purpose of the STEP project only and when used in publications or presentations they will be completely anonymised.

FOR FURTHER INFORMATION

ADD YOUR DETAILS HERE

The STEP researchers will be glad to answer your questions about the co-design session and the project at any time. You may contact them as follows:

Dr Paula Forbes – HCI Researcher Abertay University Dundee (UK)

p.forbes@abertay.ac.uk

D3.2: Integrated and Tested STEP Platform

+441382308633

OR

Dr. Stefano De Paoli – Sociologist, Abertay University Dundee (UK)

s.depaoli@abertay.ac.uk

+441382308446

http://www.abertay.ac.uk/research/staff/s_depaoli/

Information is also available online at : <http://step4youth.eu/>

Appendix A.2

PARTICIPANT INFORMED CONSENT (to be given along with information sheet)

Project: STEP- SocieTal and political Engagement of young People in environmental issues

Researchers Details: Paula Forbes - Research Fellow [p.forbes@abertay.ac.uk]

Stefano De Paoli – Lecturer in Sociology [s.depaoli@abertay.ac.uk]

Please tick the following boxes:

I confirm that I have received sufficient information about the STEP project and about my participation in this activity.	<input type="checkbox"/>
I understand that my participation in STEP research is voluntary and at any time during the time period of the activity I can withdraw.	<input type="checkbox"/>
I agree to participate in this activity.	<input type="checkbox"/>
I agree that the information created will be used to inform the project about engagement with environmental issues and policies.	<input type="checkbox"/>
I agree for the researchers to use the material produced in future scientific publications.	<input type="checkbox"/>
I agree that the data gathered in this activity may be stored (in a secure and anonymised form) by the researcher for future research and publication.	<input type="checkbox"/>

Name of Participant: _____ DOB _____

Date: _____

Signature: _____

Appendix A.3

CO-DESIGN PARENTAL CONSENT FORM

INTRODUCTION

Your child has been invited to participate in a Design session for an EU project called STEP. This project *SocieTal and political Engagement of young People in environmental issues* (STEP) seeks to engage young people in discussions about environmental policies, in particular offering an opportunity to discuss their ideas with policymakers, with an online platform, via social media and mobile applications. The project is funded by the European Commission Under the call YOUNG-5b-2014: "Societal and political engagement of young people and their perspectives on Europe".

During the coming months, as part of the project we will conduct some co-design sessions with both policy makers and young people across Europe. These sessions will help us define and shape the form of the online platform we are creating. Your child will therefore have the opportunity to be part of this interesting project and their input will be considered for the design of the platform.

WHAT IS INVOLVED IN THE CO-DESIGN SESSION?

Your child will be asked to come up with ideas for the design of the interface for the platform. We think this will take him/her between 1.5 -2 hours. The session will be led by a researcher (Dr Paula Forbes) from the University of Abertay (<http://www.abertay.ac.uk>) a University based in Scotland, and supported by XX from XX . It will be conducted in English with support from Albert who is fluent in both languages. The session should not carry any major discomfort. All the tasks will be paper based and focused on engagement with environmental issues and social media. Should any task provide discomfort your child will always have the right to refuse to participate.

BENEFITS TO TAKING PART IN THE SESSION?

At this stage, our goal is to involve the users early in the design process and empower them to contribute actively to the final shape of the STEP platform. The users/participants who take part will have a relevant role in shaping how the STEP platform will be developed. Indeed our research goal is to listen and make sure that the user's needs are taken in account in the development process.

CONFIDENTIALITY/ANONYMITY

The data collected will contain minimal personal information about your child except their age and gender. Any designs and material produced in the session will be used for the purpose of the STEP project only and if used in publications or presentations they will be completely anonymised.

THEIR RIGHTS AS A RESEARCH PARTICIPANT

Participation in this co-design session is voluntary. Your child has the right not to participate at all or to leave the session at any time. Deciding not to participate or choosing to leave the session will not result in any penalty or loss of benefits to which your child is entitled, and it will not harm his/her relationship with the school.

PARENTAL PERMISSION FOR YOUR CHILD TO PARTICIPATE IN THE CO-DESIGN SESSION

As parent or legal guardian, I authorize _____ (child's name) to participate in the co-design session described in this form.

Child's Date of Birth

Parent or Legal Guardian's Signature

Date

PARTICIPATION

Your participation will always be voluntary and as participant you can withdraw at any time from the research. On this occasion, we aim at conducting a design session lasting between 1.5 – 2 hours.

The session will be conducted in the school environment and will be done in English (with support from a native Spanish/Catalan speaker). The session will be conducted by a professional researcher from Abertay (<http://www.abertay.ac.uk>) a University based in Scotland.

FOR FURTHER INFORMATION

Information about the STEP project is available online at : <http://step4youth.eu/>

ADD YOUR CONTACT DETAILS HERE

The STEP researchers will be happy to answer your questions about the co-design session and the project at any time. You may contact them as follows:

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